

D12.3: Initial Infrastructure Implementation Report

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Acronyms and abbreviations

ACDM	ARIADNE Catalogue Data Model (see Annex)
API	Application Programming Interface
BC/AD	Before Christ / Anno Domini, i.e. dates before / after Jesus's birth
CIDOC	International Committee for Documentation of the International Council of Museums
CIDOC-CRM	CIDOC - Conceptual Reference Model; ISO 21127:2006 standard: A reference ontology for the interchange of cultural heritage information
CRUD	Create, Read, Update, Delete operations conducted through a REST API (see below)
CSS3	Cascading Style Sheets (level 3)
DC	Dublin Core (metadata standard)
DCAT	Data Catalog Vocabulary, an RDF vocabulary designed to facilitate interoperability between data catalogs published on the Web
GIS	Geographical Information Systems / Services
HTML	HyperText Markup Language
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ISO/IEC 11179	International standard for representing metadata for an organization in a metadata registry
Java / Javascript	Programming languages
JDBC	Java Database Connectivity
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
lat/lon	Latitude and longitude coordinates
LDAP	Lightweight Directory Access Protocol
LOD	Linked Open Data
Log4J	A Java-based logging package
METS	Metadata Encoding and Transmission Standard
MySQL	An open source relational database management system
OAI	Open Archives Initiative

OAI-PMH	OAI - Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
OAI-ORE	OAI - Object Reuse and Exchange Specification
OAuth	Authentication protocol
ODBC	Open Database Connectivity
PHP	PHP Hypertext Preprocessor (server-side scripting language for making dynamic and interactive web pages)
RDF	Resource Description Framework
REST	Representational State Transfer
REST API	RESTful Application Programming Interface
REST services	RESTful web services
SAML	Security Assertion Markup Language
SKOS	Simple Knowledge Organization System
SKOSify	Transforming a thesaurus, classification system or other knowledge organization system into the SKOS format
SPARQL	SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language
SQL	Structured Query Language
Syslog	Standard for computer message logging
UI	User Interface
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
WGS84	World Geodetic System 1984
XML	Extensible Markup Language
XSD	XML Schema Definition Language

1 Executive Summary

This document is a deliverable (D12.3 Initial Infrastructure Implementation Report) of the ARIADNE project (“Advanced Research Infrastructure for Archaeological Dataset Networking in Europe”), which is funded under the European Community's Seventh Framework Programme. It presents results of the work carried out in Task 12.3 “Implementing Integration”.

The overall architecture of the ARIADNE infrastructure has been laid down by the user requirements analysis (D12.1) and the infrastructure specifications (D12.2). The goal of the ARIADNE infrastructure is to integrate data and metadata from different providers into one common schema, and also to provide semantic integration along different axes (e.g. subject, space, time). This integration intends to provide useful and user-friendly information services for archaeology. The services are intended to be available not only to researchers and related stakeholders, but also to a wider range of potential users requiring access to collections and datasets.

The main goal of Task 12.3 is to present the initial infrastructure implementation of ARIADNE. The infrastructure is specified on D12.2 and includes services such as the registry, vocabulary services, metadata enrichment services, preservation services, etc. with the following components:

- a) an RDF store
- b) the first version of the portal
- c) the MORe aggregation infrastructure
- d) an Elasticsearch component
- e) a metadata quality measurement service
- f) a set of enrichment services

Task 12.3 and this report focusses on the description of core services. The core services are described and implemented as individual service components in the overall architecture, and their complementary role is presented. Task 12.3 will be followed by Task 12.4 Testing (which will be reported on in D12.4 Initial infrastructure testing report). This will be followed by another round of implementation and testing in Tasks 12.5 and 12.6.

The API specifications presented in the Annexes are especially important, as they allow developers to build on the infrastructure and deploy services. The APIs presented are REST-based and require data formats such as JSON, XML and RDF.

The development process of the ARIADNE portal (and other services) is an ongoing process. The initial approach and development is presented in a section nine.

2 Objectives

The main objectives of WP12 are:

- To adapt infrastructures provided to ARIADNE for integration
- To design, implement and configure the necessary mechanisms (crosswalks, mappings) and resources for interoperability
- To set up the internal (APIs) and external (human) interfaces to access the integrated resources

WP12 comprises the following tasks:

- Task 12.1 Assessment of Use Requirements
- Task 12.2 Design and Specifications
- Task 12.3 Implementing Integration
- Task 12.4 Testing

The main goal of Task 12.3 is to present the initial infrastructure implementation of ARIADNE. The infrastructure is specified on D12.2 and includes services such as the registry, vocabulary services, metadata enrichment services, preservation services, etc. (fig. 1).

Figure 1. The ARIADNE data integration architecture.

This deliverable reports the results of Task 12.3. It consists of a report on the implementation of the core components of the infrastructure. The final implementation will be reported in D12.5.

3 Overall Architecture

The overall architecture of the ARIADNE infrastructure has been laid down by the user requirements analysis (D12.1) and the infrastructure specifications (D12.2). The goal of the ARIADNE infrastructure is to integrate data and metadata from different providers into one common schema, and also to provide semantic integration along different axes (e.g. subject, space, time). This integration intends to provide useful and user-friendly information services for archaeology. The services are intended to be available not only to researchers and related stakeholders, but also to a wider range of potential users requiring access to collections and datasets.

Deliverable D12.1 “User Requirements” [1], which outlines the user needs for the interoperability framework of the ARIADNE Infrastructure, sets out a general view of the integration functionalities, organized in four successive levels (fig. 2) [1]. At Level 1, data is created by research projects and groups, subsequently stored in institutional repositories at Level 2. Then, at Level 3, this data is aggregated by higher level data managers such as data centers, portals and thematic information gates. Finally, at Level 4, the ARIADNE infrastructure integrates all information and provides a set of services through the ARIADNE portal. These services include: resource discovery, integrated data search, and other services (such as preservation, quality, etc.).

Figure 2. The ARIADNE data integration architecture.

The ARIADNE infrastructure services aim to provide useful services and tools to the archaeological community. Thus, a simple yet effective portal design is imperative in order to achieve these goals. This portal (seen in Figure 4) consists of three main pillars:

- a) Resource discovery
- b) Data integration services
- c) Other services

The resource discovery services rely directly on the registry, whereas the data integration services provide more intelligent ways of data integration through LOD and NLP technologies or through the ARIADNE CRM (conceptual reference model).

The services that will facilitate the integration (fig. 3) consist of the following components, and are described in detail in Deliverable D12.2:

- the ARIADNE catalog
- integration & interoperability service
- a deposit service
- a metadata enrichment service
- a metadata quality service
- vocabulary services
- preservation services
- resource discovery services
- configuration & management service
- digital assets management service
- preview services
- the ARIADNE portal

Figure 3. The ARIADNE data integration architecture

The initial implementation of the infrastructure focuses on the creation and aggregation of content according to the ACDM model specification [4] (the current version is 2.5.5). According to the content aggregation workflow (fig. 4), the MORE aggregator (see respective section below) is used to harvest existing content in other schemas and map it to ACDM, or import directly from batches of XML or Excel files. ACDM encoded information is then pushed to an RDF store and to the Registry service. Another service is used to synchronize content from the RDF store to an Elasticsearch index service. The rest of the services within the infrastructure consume these three APIs in order to access / manage this information. The APIs are:

1. The RDF store SPARQL endpoint
2. The Registry REST API
3. The Elasticsearch API

Figure 4. The ARIADNE data aggregation workflow.

4 Aggregation Service

The aggregation service is comprised of a set of tools and services that aim to harvest content related to archaeology, clean and transform it to a common format (in this case the ACDM). This content is then stored persistently in an RDF store and an index server. This process is integral to the data integration process of the project, which focuses on integration of data scattered amongst diverse collections, datasets, unpublished fieldwork reports (grey literature), and publications. This provides researchers with the ability to use heterogeneous distributed datasets as an integral component of archaeological research methodologies. Content aggregation is necessary in order to map all content available by the ARIADNE partners in a common schema (in this case, the ACDM), so as to facilitate the integration process. Aggregation includes a number of steps, such as validation, cleaning and enrichment.

In order to address these requirements, the Metadata & Object Repository (MORe) aggregator [6] has been employed in ARIADNE (<http://more.dcu.gr/>). MORe is described in more detail in the next section.

The MORe Aggregator

The MORe aggregator, developed by the Digital Curation Unit – IMIS, Athena R.C., has been effectively used in diverse projects (CARARE, 3D-ICONS, and LoCloud) to aggregate and enrich millions of records and deliver them to the Europeana platform (<http://www.europeana.eu>). MORe provides a flexible architecture, and is used here to aggregate content in various formats, and from a variety of sources, to the RDF store, the registry and the Elasticsearch. MORe incorporates a micro-service oriented architecture (fig. 5), supporting the following set of core services:

- Input
- Validation
- Transformation
- Enrichment
- Publication

The core services are designed in a modular way so they can combine one or more micro-services to accomplish the various tasks. This approach allows the system to be extended more easily, and also re-use certain micro-services. The stackable and modular architecture of MORe (fig. 5) presents a data access layer used to access data on the storage and a core services layer, encompassing the various core services management. The different core management services are responsible for orchestrating numerous micro-services. For example, the enrichment management services are responsible for orchestrating and streamlining the execution of the enrichment micro-services.

Figure 5. The MORE architecture.

Other important architectural aspects of the system (fig. 6) provide the capability of using multiple storage technologies simultaneously. The data access layer, which is instantiated through a storage API, provides seamless access to data objects regardless of the storage in which they reside. Two additional important components of MORE are the messaging and logging services. The messaging service is responsible for providing messaging across services. It is based on the RabbitMQ AMPQ broker, a framework which provides scalability and elasticity. The logging service provides a mechanism for monitoring all the services in the aggregation infrastructure. It is implemented based on the Graylog2 logging framework, which provides a mechanism for storing logs of any format and from any service. Graylog2 provides a way of organizing these log messages (using streams) and presenting them in a user-friendly way.

Figure 6. Significant architectural aspects of MORE.

Aggregation workflow

The main aggregation workflow is presented below (fig. 7). An information package is harvested by a micro-service and is pre-validated (pre-validation includes basic validation, such as a record to be structurally checked to see if it is well formed). The package can be either deleted or ingested. During ingest, the package is stored in the storage layer (it first goes into temporary storage), and then it can be either rejected or transformed into a common schema (in this case the ACDM). During transformation, the new representation is validated and indexed. After it has been transformed, the package can be rejected, enriched or published. In the case of enrichment, a new representation is created (enriched ACDM), which has to be validated and indexed again. During the publishing process the user selects the publication target.

In the case of ARIADNE, the intermediate schema is ACDM. The publication targets that may be used are:

- Publish to Elasticsearch
- Publish to Virtuoso RDF Store
- Publish to Registry API

Figure 7. Aggregation workflow.

5 Data Access & Management Services

The data access management services have a layer that provides different ways of allowing access to the available data sources. These are: native access to the RDF store, access through an Elasticsearch and through the Registry. Although they access the same information, each might contain only a subset (e.g. Elasticsearch), or provide access through different protocols and formats.

Furthermore, as ARIADNE will enable trans-national access of researchers to data centres, tools and guidance, it is important to provide multiple access points in the data sources. This means that through the data access management services, researchers can preview their datasets in different formats, such as RDF, JSON or XML.

RDF Store

The RDF store holds the catalog information represented in RDF and available through a SPARQL endpoint. Taking into account the complexity of the ACDM, an RDF representation of the ARIADNE Catalog is necessary to support the complex queries required. For that reason, the ACDM can be represented as RDF and URIs are assigned for each type of resource.

The data in the RDF store is updated by MORE dynamically during content aggregation. Two main technologies have been considered and can be used:

1. Sesame (<http://rdf4j.org/>)
2. Virtuoso (<http://virtuoso.openlinksw.com/>)

Sesame is provided as a single .war file that installs easily in Tomcat whereas Virtuoso is provided through a complete stack with its own internal server and APIs. Among the two, Virtuoso was selected primarily due its better performance, especially when handling large amounts of content. In addition, Virtuoso has been available since 1998, as opposed to Sesame, which was released in 2004. Virtuoso is also available in many programming languages (.Net, C, C#, C++, Java, JavaScript, Perl, PHP, Python, Ruby, Visual Basic) whereas Sesame is available to Java, PHP and Python. The most important characteristics that make Virtuoso more favourable over Sesame are its capability to partition the data and being able to be setup in a clustered environment. The SPARQL endpoint and a screenshot can be seen below.

SPARQL Console for Virtuoso:

<http://ariadne-registry.dcu.gr:8890/sparql>

Virtuoso SPARQL Query Editor

Default Data Set Name (Graph IRI)

Query Text

```
select distinct ?Concept where {[ ] a ?Concept} LIMIT 100
```

Results Format: HTML

Execution timeout: 0 milliseconds (values less than 1000 are ignored)

Options: Strict checking of void variables

Run Query Reset

Copyright © 2015 OpenLink Software
Virtuoso version 06.01.3127 on Linux (x86_64-pc-linux-gnu), Single Server Edition

Figure 8. Screenshot of the ARIADNE SPARQL endpoint.

In order to store the entire catalog in RDF, an RDF representation of ACDM must be defined. This is accomplished through a simple mapping process handled internally by the MORE aggregator.

Elasticsearch

The Elasticsearch component provides the indexing capabilities required in order to power the ARIADNE portal. Elasticsearch (ES) is based on the well-known Lucene indexing engine (the same that SolR uses) and provides extremely low response times for performing full text search and faceted browsing. The two main reasons for selecting Elasticsearch over other traditional interfaces to SolR are its simple and effective RESTful API and its clustering capabilities. Elasticsearch provides very robust and easy to use clustering support.

The primary format that Elasticsearch accepts through its API is JSON. That means that all ACDM records must be first mapped into JSON in order to be pushed to ES.

Elasticsearch REST API:

http://ariadne-registry.dcu.gr:9200/_search

Figure 9. Screenshot showing Elasticsearch REST interface through Web http client.

Since the primary mission of ES is to facilitate the Resource Discovery section of the ARIADNE Portal, only the features associated with this functionality will be kept. Furthermore, the search results should be specified in a way that minimises subsequent API calls. An example of such a record can be seen in the table below.

Example of a JSON representation of an ACDM record

```

{
  _index: "dataresources",
  _type: "dataset",
  _id: "46949",
  _score: 1,
  _source: {
    accessRights: "Unrestricted access for all registered EASY
users.",
    modified: "2010-01-11",
    distribution: {
      id: 46,
      title: "EASY OAI-PMH",
      modified: "2014-01-01",
      issued: "2014-01-01",
      description: "EASY OAI-PMH Endpoint",
      OAI-PMHServerURI: "http://easy.dans.knaw.nl/oai/",
    },
  },

```

```

    type: "dataset",
    description: "Onderzoeks- en adviesbureau voor Bouwhistorie,
Archeologie, Architectuur- en Cultuurhistorie (BAAC bv) heeft een
archeologisch bureauonderzoek en inventariserend veldonderzoek met
behulp van boringen (karterende fase) uitgevoerd op een terrein in
de bebouwde kom van Tilburg. Tijdens het veldonderzoek is
aangetoond dat de bodem is verstoord tot in de Chorizont van de
dekzandafzettingen. Archeologische indicatoren werden daarbij niet
aangetroffen. De verwachte duinvaaggronden zijn niet aangetroffen.
Hieruit kan worden geconcludeerd dat aan het plangebied een lage
archeologische verwachting voor archeologische resten uit alle
perioden kan worden toegekend.",
    rights: "BAAC bv",
    id: 46949,
    language: ["nl"],
    subject: "Event/intervention databases",
    title: "Tilburg Bredaseweg 421",
    originalId: "DMO_ID easy-dataset:22059",
    keyword: ["50F", "Bredaseweg 421", "Tilburg", "Noord-Brabant"],
    creator: [{
      id: 480,
      name: "Boshoven, E.H.",
      type: "person"
    }],
    spatial: [{
      id: 34449,
      coordinate_system:
"http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSSG/0/4326",
      lon: 5.04075,
      label: "51.55941102,5.04075138",
      lat: 51.5594
    }],
    landingPage: "http://www.persistent-
identifier.nl/urn:nbn:nl:ui:13-dox-y9f",
    issued: "2008-01"
  }
}

```

Registry

The registry service is a single point where all ARIADNE resources are stored and made available. It provides access to all ACDM records, and allows users to create/edit them both through a REST interface and through a Web UI. The registry consists of an SQL database and a REST API that provides access to the data. The users can register an API key and use the REST API to perform CRUD operations on all entities. An example of an API call can be seen below.

Get Data Resources

Get all the Data Resources of the registry using some filters if necessary.

Method	GET http://ariadne-registry.dcu.gr:8080/ariadneWeb/api/v1/dataResources									
Content Type	application/json									
Request	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Parameter</th> <th>Data Type</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>key</td> <td>String</td> <td>The API key of the user</td> </tr> <tr> <td>typeid</td> <td>Integer</td> <td>The type of the Data Resources (0:Collections 1:Datasets 2:Databases 3:GIS)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Parameter	Data Type	Description	key	String	The API key of the user	typeid	Integer	The type of the Data Resources (0:Collections 1:Datasets 2:Databases 3:GIS)
Parameter	Data Type	Description								
key	String	The API key of the user								
typeid	Integer	The type of the Data Resources (0:Collections 1:Datasets 2:Databases 3:GIS)								
Response	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Parameter</th> <th>Data Type</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>id</td> <td>Integer</td> <td>The id of each Data Resource</td> </tr> <tr> <td>name</td> <td>String</td> <td>The name of each Data Resource</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Parameter	Data Type	Description	id	Integer	The id of each Data Resource	name	String	The name of each Data Resource
Parameter	Data Type	Description								
id	Integer	The id of each Data Resource								
name	String	The name of each Data Resource								
Status	200 – SUCCESS 500 – INTERNAL_SERVER_ERROR									

Example

```
Request: {"key":"tUzQwU2T1RqBRuHC1ENJmtaopTMfWF6sHE7OrjRPzr98DiB","typeid":"1"}
Response: [{"id":20,"name":"CulturalItalia - Archaeology"}, {"id":33,"name":"Archaeological materials"}]
```

The full API documentation is provided in Annex II. The Web UI has been presented and documented in the ACDM model specification report.

Users without any content in an existing format and available through a repository can use the registry service to catalogue content from scratch, manually or through the REST API.

The technology used to create the registry is based on PHP and MySQL, and was selected for three main reasons:

- It is the same as that selected for building the ARIADNE Portal (see respective section below);
- It is ideal for quickly matching the continuous changes of the ACDM; and,
- It has a small learning curve (allowing more developers to start quickly)

6 Validation Services

This section documents the list of services that could be used to perform validation on the ACDM XSD. Validation is performed during content ingest and creation and is facilitated automatically by MORE. All validation services provide a reporting mechanism through the UI to alert the user.

Figure 10. Screenshot of the thematic and spatial validation service.

Apart from the standard validation reporting mechanism, when a certain type of information is detected (spatial, temporal, thematic), respective blocks of information appear alerting the user visually. An example for thematic and spatial information can be seen in the screenshot above.

Schema Validation

This service provides schema validation for every XML record ingested. This functionality is automatically provided by MORE. Schema validation requires an XSD (in this case ACDM XSD).

Normalization

This service performs normalization of the ingested datasets. This process ensures the proper identity management of each resource by matching provider and collection information, along with native identifiers, etc.

Figure 11. The aggregation workflow normalization perspective.

Link Checking

The link checking service requires a list of elements that contain URLs, for which it attempts to check if the links are available (or, else, it returns an HTTP error code). This service is already provided by MORE, but requires a list of elements to check. Elements which may contain links and which need to be checked have to be marked beforehand.

Schematron Rule Validation

This service performs more complex checks on an XML record. It provides a mechanism to perform complex conditional checks, and also provide feedback back to the user in a human-readable mechanism. The mechanism is provided by MORE but requires a Schematron rule for ACDM. A sample Schematron rule validation report can be seen in the screenshot below.

Figure 12. Screenshot of a sample Schematron rule validation report.

7 Metadata Enrichment Services

The metadata enrichment service consists of a series of micro-services that can be used effectively to augment ACDM content. These micro-services can be either used as enrichment services in MORE, or directly by the ARIADNE partners and services. In this section, a list of available micro-services is presented.

Once the metadata enrichment services are registered in MORE, users can utilize them by incorporating them into enrichment plans. Enrichment plans are a way of streamlining and executing enrichment services together. They apply to one schema and can be re-used in different packages. This means users can define them once, and apply them for all incoming packages with the same characteristics.

Although enrichment services can perform a wide variety of operations, they are presented in this section in four categories:

- Subject
- Space
- Time
- Other

Subject

The thematic services focus on enriching subject-related information. This enrichment process can be either automatic (e.g. by automatically matching concepts from vocabularies) or manually (by allowing users to create collections of concepts and attach them to all items in a package). All thematic enrichment services have access to the large number of vocabularies listed in Annex III. These vocabularies are standardised, published and SKOSified, and contain hundreds of thousands of terms.

The browsing and searching for these vocabularies can be accomplished either through a REST API or through the MORE UI. An example of the latter case can be seen in the screenshot below.

Other subject-related services have access to other resources such as Wikipedia and DBpedia lemmas.

Figure 13. Screenshot of a browsing for vocabularies in the MORE UI.

In the following tables, the implemented subject related enrichment services are presented.

Service:	Subject collections
Status:	Provided as a service through MORE
Description:	This service allows the user to create collections of subject terms from standardized thesauri. These subject collections are then used to enrich the items of a package (by adding the concepts of the collection to the items of the package).

Service:	Automatic metadata enrichment
Status:	Provided as a service through MORE
Description:	A string (e.g. dc:subject or dc:description) is submitted to the service and a list of relevant concept terms are retrieved (based on a list of 29 SKOS vocabularies). The element dc:subject is updated.

Service:	DBPedia and Wikipedia automatic enrichment
Status:	Provided as a service through MORE
Description:	A string (e.g. dc:title, dc:subject or dc:description) is submitted to the service and a list of relevant Wikipedia and DBPedia URLs are retrieved. An open-annotations based list (RDF encoded) is returned that annotates the text.

Translation of subject terms to AAT

In order to ensure interoperability and facilitate integration, all ACMD records must contain AAT terms (AAT stand for Arts and Architecture Thesaurus, and refers to the faceted thesaurus developed by the Getty Foundation and intended for “vocabulary control of museum, cultural heritage and art collections”).

For this reason, a translation service, developed by the Hypermedia Research Group at the University of South Wales, is provided to allow partners to upload their native subject terms/vocabularies, map them

to the AAT, and export a mapping file. This mapping service produces the mapping rules in various formats (such as JSON and CSV). The tool is available at:

<http://heritagedata.org/vocabularyMatchingTool/>

It is accessible as a web application (thus only a web browser is needed). The intuitive UI design (seen in the screenshot below) uses two columns (left for the source vocabulary, right for the target vocabulary).

Vocabulary Matching Tool

The screenshot displays the Vocabulary Matching Tool interface, which is organized into two main columns: Source Vocabulary and Target Vocabulary.

Source Vocabulary: (FISH Archaeological Objects Thesaurus)

- Input: Arch
- Buttons: ARCH, Archetype, ARCHITECTURAL ELEMENT, ARCHITECTURAL FRAGMENT, ARCHITECTURE, FINIAL (ARCHITECTURAL), PARCHMENT, PARCHMENT PRICKER, PIPE (ARCHITECTURAL)
- Matched: ARCHITECTURE → ARCHITECTURAL FRAGMENT
- Description: Fragments of a structure, usually material that has been worked.
- Buttons: BOARD, BRICK, CAME, CERAMIC, DAUB, DRESSED STONE, FIRE STONE, FLAGSTONE, FLASHING, PALING, PLANK, ROOF SLAB, SHINGLE, STRUCTURAL TIMBER, TESSERA, TILE, WALL PLASTER

Target Vocabulary: (Getty Art & Architecture Thesaurus)

- Input: Brick
- Buttons: <brick by form: shape or size>, <brick by form: solidity>, <brick by form>, <brick by function>, <brick by location or context>, <brick by technique: drying process>
- Matched: <brick by form> → <brick by form: shape or size>
- Buttons: angle brick, brick slip, brickbat, bull-nose brick, bullnose brick, compass brick, cutter (brick), dog-leg brick, dogleg brick, great brick, jumbo brick, modular brick, Norman brick, plinth brick, Roman brick, soap (brick)

Concept Matching:

- Source: ARCHITECTURAL FRAGMENT
- Match Type: close match
- Target: <brick by form: shape or size>
- Button: ADD MATCH

Export Options: CLEAR, LOAD, SAVE, EXPORT (TRIG), EXPORT (CSV)

Figure 14. Screenshot of the Vocabulary Matching Tool.

After the user has defined the concept mappings, they can save and export them in various formats. An example of a JSON encoded mapping can be seen in the table below.

```
[
{
  "created": "2015-04-14T13:57:18.206Z",
  "sourceURI": "http://purl.org/heritagedata/schemes/mda_obj/concepts/96909",
  "sourceLabel": "ADZE",
  "targetURI": "http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300023553",
  "targetLabel": "adzes",
  "matchURI": "http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#closeMatch",
  "matchLabel": "close match",
  "notes": "",
  "creator": "anonymous"
},
{
  "created": "2015-05-11T14:25:15.011Z",
  "sourceURI": "http://purl.org/heritagedata/schemes/mda_obj/concepts/95253",
  "sourceLabel": "COMPASS",
  "targetURI": "http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300196707",
  "targetLabel": "compasses (direction indicators)",
  "matchURI": "http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#closeMatch",
  "matchLabel": "close match",
  "notes": "",
  "creator": "anonymous"
}
]
```

Users can then upload this translation file into the MORE subject translation enrichment service, which is currently under development, and use it to automatically translate their native subject terms to AAT.

Space

The space related enrichment services focus on enriching spatial content and currently they perform four main tasks:

- Geo-coding
- Reverse geo-coding
- Coordinate translation
- Geo-normalization

The various available micro-services can be seen in the tables below.

Service:	Geonames
Status:	Provided as a service through MORE
Description:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A string (e.g. place Label) is submitted for geo-coding and the Latitude/Longitude coordinates are returned. The lat/lon elements are updated. 2. A set of lat/lon coordinates are submitted and a place name is returned. The place name is updated. <p>API available at: http://api.geonames.org/</p>

Service:	DAI Gazetteer
Status:	Provided as a service through MORE
Description:	<p>A string (e.g. placeLabel) is submitted for geo-coding and the lat/lon coordinates are returned. The lat/lon elements are updated.</p> <p>API available at: http://gazetteer.dainst.org/search</p>

Service:	Pelagios
Status:	Provided as a service through MORE
Description:	The Pelagios ancient place names service allows resolving ancient place names to modern names. API available at: http://pelagios.org/api-v3/search

Service:	British National Grid → WGS84 Transformation
Status:	Provided as a service through MORE
Description:	A string containing the grid coordinates is submitted for transformation and the WGS84 lat/lon coordinates are returned. The lat/lon elements are updated.

Service:	Transformation between EPSG codes
Status:	Provided as a service through MORE
Description:	The lat/lon coordinates are transformed from an EPSG code to another. The lat/lon elements are updated.

Service:	Geo-normalization
Status:	Provided as a service through MORE
Description:	A string that contains a concatenated string of coordinates is submitted for geo-normalization. The user indicates the delimiter and the lat/lon coordinates are returned. The lat/lon elements are updated.

Time

Currently there are no time related enrichment services implemented in MORE. ARIADNE partners are currently contributing to the PeriodO gazetteer of period assertions, and PeriodO URIs will be available for integration into MORE shortly. More information can be found at <http://perio.do/>.

Service:	PeriodO
Status:	Under development – Will be provided as a service through MORE
Description:	The PeriodO service provides a SKOSified collection of period names. This makes it possible to resolve period names to absolute dates. Period names are encoded differently depending parameters such as the geographical coverage.

Other

This section currently includes a language identification service to automatically detect language information based on text. It is based on Apache Tika and contains trained models for all major languages.

Service:	Language Identification
Status:	Provided as a service through MORE
Description:	This service detects the language in which a piece of text is written. A text element is submitted and the language is returned. The xml:lang attribute is updated.

8 Metadata Quality Services

This section aims at documenting the list of services that could be used to provide quality related information for ACDM records. These metadata quality services mainly focus on completeness and consistency.

Completeness

Completeness refers to metadata completeness, estimated for an entire package (at item level) and falls under two separate cases:

1. Completeness of important elements
2. Completeness of mandatory/recommended element sets

The first case aims to visually provide the completeness of a list of the 10-15 most important elements of the ACDM.

The second case aims to provide information on the completeness of all elements, using two facets: mandatory and recommended sets.

Figure 15. Metadata quality information provided to the user.

Consistency

This service allows the checking of certain elements for consistency issues. Consistency refers to the following cases:

1. URL format checking (for example: elements like `rdf:about` should have a URL as value)
2. Date format (based on ISO dates format)
3. Person names (regex patterns that could detect patterns such as: Name Surname, Title Name Surname, etc.)

Figure 16. Metadata quality information provided to the user.

9 ARIADNE Portal

This section presents the initial implementation of the ARIADNE portal.

Mock-ups

A series of mock-ups were created to start a discussion on the design and functionalities of the ARIADNE portal, and to act as a guideline for implementation. These mockups present a design with three different sections: Browse, Search and Services. The Browse section will act as a starting point for exploring the ARIADNE Info Space in different geo, time and subject based visualizations. The Search section will present a classic information retrieval interface for the different types of resources in the ARIADNE Catalog, and will be complemented using facet-based search. The Services section will provide access to the different services developed in the project as part of WP13.

Figure 17: Mockup of the portal's home page.

Figure 18: A search results page with faceted browsing/filtering.

Figure 19: A demo of combining subject, place and time.

Figure 20. A page showing map-based browsing.

Figure 21: A page showing browsing through a timeline.

Technologies

Although the ARIADNE portal is designed to be modular, the main framework selected for its implementation is Laravel (<http://laravel.com/>). Laravel is a PHP based framework designed to facilitate the development of model-view-controller (MVC) applications. Laravel is open source and already provides a good number of services, as can be seen from the table below:

- Authentication
- Billing
- Cache
- Collections
- Command Bus
- Core Extension
- Elixir
- Encryption
- Hashing
- Helpers
- Localization
- Mail
- Package Development
- Pagination
- Queues
- Session

- Envoy
- Errors & Logging
- Events
- Filesystem/Cloud Storage
- Templates
- Unit Testing
- Validation

Prototype

An initial implementation of the ARIADNE portal using the above technologies is shown in the following screenshots. They present the initial implementation which is currently being used by partners to inspect their content and is gradually evolving according to the mockups presented in the previous section. The prototype is based on a Bootstrap 3.0 responsive theme and design which allows use of the portal from virtually any kind of device, including:

- Workstations
- Tablets
- Smartphones

The prototype is designed using a modular architecture where each module is used to provide a specific functionality. In the current prototype, modules for the following functionalities are provided:

- Search for records
- Browse for records
- View record
- Map view
- Thematic view
- View by content provider

Welcome

ARIADNE brings together and integrates existing archaeological research data infrastructures so that researchers can use the various distributed datasets and new and powerful technologies as an integral component of the archaeological research methodology. There is now a large availability of archaeological digital datasets that, together, span different periods, domains and regions; more are continuously created as a result of the increasing use of IT. These are the accumulated outcome of the research of individuals, teams and institutions, but form a vast and fragmented corpus and their potential has been constrained by difficult access and non-homogenous perspectives.

[Visit Ariadne Infrastructure](#)

Providers

Country	Name	Collections	Datasets	Databases
	ADS	1	27471	0
	AIAC, L - P: Archaeology	0	2	0
	ARUP-CAS	0	1	0
	Beniculturali	1	10	0
	CNR	2	0	1
	CYR-STARC	1	1	0
	DANS	2	24892	0
	Incipit CSIS	0	1	0
	INRAP	1	20720	0
	MIBACT-ICCU	2	1	0
	MNM-NOK	185	1565	0
	ØAW	0	0	4
	SND	0	434	0
	UNI-Frankfurt	1	0	0
	ZRC SAZU	0	0	2

[More](#)

Figure 22: Home screen of the portal.

The screenshot shows the 'Datasets' page in the ARIADNE metadata registry. The left sidebar contains navigation options: Home, Search, Map based search, Provider info, Provider data (with a dropdown menu showing Collections, Datasets, Databases, GIS, Metadata Schemas, Services, Vocabularies, and Agents), Ariadne subject, and About. The main content area displays a table of datasets with columns for ID, Provider, and Name. A pagination bar at the bottom shows page 1 of 4993.

ID	Provider	Name
20	Beniculturali	Culturalitalia - Archaeology
22	Beniculturali	Archaeological Sites
25	MIBACT-ICCU	MIBACT-SITAR Project - Information Sources Dataset
28	Beniculturali	Archaeological Complex
29	Beniculturali	Archaeological Finds
30	AIAC, L - P: Archaeology	Fasti
31	AIAC, L - P: Archaeology	FASTI
32	Beniculturali	Numismatics
33	Beniculturali	Archaeological materials
34	Beniculturali	Stratigraphic surveys
35	Beniculturali	Archaeological Surveys
36	Beniculturali	Anthropological Finds
37	ARUP-CAS	archaeological aerial images
42	Beniculturali	Archaeological Excavations
26120	DANS	Plangebied Laagveld te Horn, gemeente Haelen

Figure 23: List of existing datasets.

The screenshot shows the search results page for the term 'archeological'. The search bar contains the text 'archeological' and a 'Search' button. Below the search bar, it indicates 'Total: 20' results. A pagination bar shows page 1 of 2. The results are displayed in a grid of six cards, each representing a dataset. Each card includes a building icon, the dataset title, its type ('dataset'), and its subject ('Fieldwork databases').

Dataset Title	Type	Subject
Boroughbridge Road, Knaresborough, Archeological Evaluation	dataset	Fieldwork databases
Agro Pontino Archeological Survey	dataset	Fieldwork databases
A45/A445 Improvements, Archeological Assessment	dataset	Fieldwork databases
Greyfriars Kirkhouse, Edinburgh: Results of an Archeological Excavation	dataset	Fieldwork databases
Land at Maulden Road, Flitwick, Bedfordshire: Archeological Field Evaluation	dataset	Fieldwork databases
Land South of sparrowhawk Road, Holton (HLN 009) Archeological Evaluation Report	dataset	Fieldwork databases

Figure 24: Search results for term 'archeological'.

10 Conclusions

This document presented the current status (initial phase) of the infrastructure implementation of the ARIADNE project. The current status and the main technical choices of the primary components that are required to set up and make the infrastructure operational have been presented. Some components have already been set up and tested whereas others are awaiting testing, using the real content to be harvested. In other cases (e.g. the PeriodO enrichment service) they are under development.

The diversity of the components required to run the infrastructure, along with the large number of services are indicative of the complexity of the infrastructure and thus it is clear that improvements on some components and the ACDM model will be required. These improvements along with the development of the rest of the services will be reported in the final progress report of WP12.

This deliverable report focused on the description of core services developed within Task 12.3. These core services were described and their complementary role is presented. Task 12.3 will now be followed by Task 12.4 Testing (which will be reported in D12.4 Initial infrastructure testing report). This will be followed by another round of implementation and testing in Tasks 12.5 and 12.6.

11 References

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11. OAI-ORE - Open Archives Initiative, Object Reuse and Exchange Specification, <http://www.openarchives.org/ore/>
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13. DCAT - Data Catalog Vocabulary, <http://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat/>
14. European Union Open Data Portal, <http://open-data.europa.eu>
15. RabbitMQ, <https://www.rabbitmq.com/>
16. GrayLog2, <https://www.graylog.org/>
17. Elasticsearch, <https://www.elastic.co/products/elasticsearch>
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20. JSON, <http://json.org/>

Annex I – MOrE API

To use the MOrE API, an API key must be first registered through the Developers' section within MOrE.

Get Metadata Sources

Get all the Metadata Sources of the MOrE aggregator using some filters if it is needed.

Method	GET http://more.locloud.eu:8080/MoRe_API/api/v1/metadataSources
Content Type	application/son
Custom Headers	X-API-Key
Request	
Response	<pre>[{"id": 38, "name": "Metadata source 3 -KAMRA", "projectId": 3, "type": "OAI_PMH"}, {"id": 134, "name": "Test - duplications", "projectId": 3, "type": "OAI_PMH"}]</pre>
Status	200 : OK 500 : INTERNAL_SERVER_ERROR

Get a specific Metadata Source

Get a specific Metadata Source of the MOrE aggregator given the id of the source.

Method	GET http://more.locloud.eu:8080/more_api/api/v1/metadataSources/{id}
Content Type	application/json
Custom Headers	X-API-Key

Request

Response `{"id":134,"format":"EDM","name":"Test_duplications","projectId":3,
"rootElement":"record","schema":"OAI_DC","set":"ARC3",
"type":"OAI_PMH",
"uri":"http://more.locloud.eu:8080/locloud/","webUrl":"" }`

Status 200 : OK
500 : INTERNAL_SERVER_ERROR

Create a Metadata Source

Create a Metadata Source in the MORE aggregator.

Method POST http://more.locloud.eu:8080/MoRe_API/api/v1/metadataSources

Content Type application/json

Custom Headers X-API-Key

Request `{"format":"EDM", "name":"Test
API","projectId":3,"rootElement":"record","schema":"OAI_DC",
"set":"ARC1", "type":"OAI_PMH",
"uri":"http://api.test.eu","webUrl":""}`

Response `{"id":172,"format":"EDM","name":"Sample
MetadataSource","projectId":3,"rootElement":"record","schema":OAI_DC,
"set":"ARC3","type":"OAI_PMH",
"uri":"http://sample.locloud.eu:8080/locloud/","webUrl":""}`

Status 201 : CREATED
500 : INTERNAL_SERVER_ERROR

Get Packages

Get all the packages of the MORE aggregator.

Method	GET http://more.locloud.eu:8080/MoRe_API/api/v1/packages
Content Type	application/json
Custom Headers	X-API-Key
Request	
Response	<pre>[{"id": 1144, "schema": "OAI_DC", "sourceId": 133, "status": "Rejected" }, {"id": 1146, "schema": "OAI_DC", "sourceId": 134, "status": "Published"}, {"id": 1149, "schema": "OAI_DC", "sourceId": 134, "status": "Enriched"}]</pre>
Status	200 : OK 500 : INTERNAL_SERVER_ERROR

Get a specific Package

Get details for a specific package of the MORE aggregator, given an id.

Method	GET http://more.locloud.eu:8080/MoRe_API/api/v1/packages/{packageId}
Content Type	application/json
Custom Headers	X-MoRe-API-Key
Request	

Response	<pre>{ "id": 1146, "itemsCount": 11, "itemsEnriched": 0, "itemsIngedted": 11, "itemsPublished": 0, "itemsTransformed": 0, "pubDatastreamId": 0, "rightsId": 0, "schema": "OAI_DC", "sourceId": 134, "status": "Published" }</pre>
-----------------	---

Status	200 : OK 500 : INTERNAL_SERVER_ERROR
---------------	---

Get package datastreams

Get datastreams for a specific package of the MORE aggregator, given an id.

Method	GET http://more.locloud.eu:8080/MoRe_API/api/v1/packages/{packageId}/datasreams/{schema}
---------------	---

Content Type	application/json
---------------------	------------------

Custom Headers	X-API-Key
-----------------------	-----------

Request

Response	<pre>[{ "itemId": 5322222, "uri": "http://more.locloud.eu/rest_get_item.php?package=1146&schema=OAI_DC&file=5322222.xml" }, { "itemId": 5322223, "uri": "http://more.locloud.eu/rest_get_item.php?package=1146&schema=OAI_DC&file=5322223.xml" }]</pre>
-----------------	---

Status	200 : OK 500 : INTERNAL_SERVER_ERROR
---------------	---

Get package tasks

Get the tasks completed for a specific package of the MORE aggregator, given an id.

Method GET http://more.locloud.eu:8080/MoRe_API/api/v1/packages/{packageId}/tasks

Content Type application/json

Custom Headers X-API-Key

Request

Response [
 {"desc": "Package 498 is ready for ingestion.", "timestamp": "2014-10-14 12:49:34.0"}
]

Status 200 : OK
 500 : INTERNAL_SERVER_ERROR

Get package notifications

Get the notifications created for a specific package of the MORE aggregator, given an id.

Method GET http://more.locloud.eu:8080/MoRe_API/api/v1/packages/{packageId}/notifications

Content Type application/json

Custom Headers X-API-Key

Request

Response [
 {"desc": "A new package [498] has been created.", "timestamp": "2014-10-14 12:49:14.0"},
]

```

{"desc": "Harvest complete for package 498", "timestamp": "2014-10-14
12:49:24.0"},
{"desc": "Validation complete for package 498", "timestamp": "2014-10-14
12:49:34.0"}
]

```

Status 200 : OK
500 : INTERNAL_SERVER_ERROR

Harvest a Package

Harvest a package to the MORE aggregator.

Method POST http://more.locloud.eu:8080/MoRe_API/api/v1/metadataSources/{id}/harvest

Content Type application/json

Custom Headers X-API-Key

Request

Response { "packageId": 1299, "schema": "OAI_DC", "sourceId": 134 }

Status 201 : CREATED
500 : INTERNAL_SERVER_ERROR

Ingest a Package

Ingest a package to the MORE aggregator.

Method POST http://more.locloud.eu:8080/MoRe_API/api/v1/packages/{packageId}/ingest

Content Type application/json

Custom Headers X-API-Key

Request

Response {"msg": "Ingest request received.", "packageId": 1299, "schema": "OAI_DC", "sourceId": 134 }

Status 201 : CREATED
500 : INTERNAL_SERVER_ERROR

Transform a Package

Transform a package of the MORE aggregator.

Method POST http://more.locloud.eu:8080/MoRe_API/api/v1/packages/{packageId}/transform

Content Type application/json

Custom Headers X-API-Key

Request {"mappingId": 5, "rightsId": 1}

Response {"msg": "Transform request received.", "packageId": 1299, "mappingId": 5, "rightsId": 1}

Status 201 : CREATED
500 : INTERNAL_SERVER_ERROR

Enrich a Package

Enrich a package of the MORE aggregator.

Method POST http://more.locloud.eu:8080/MoRe_API/api/v1/packages/{packageId}/enrich

Content Type	application/json
---------------------	------------------

Custom Headers	X-API-Key
-----------------------	-----------

Request	<code>{"enrichPlanId":22}</code>
----------------	----------------------------------

Response	<code>{"msg": "Enrich request received.", "packageId":1299, "enrichPlanId":22 }</code>
-----------------	--

Status	201 : CREATED 500 : INTERNAL_SERVER_ERROR
---------------	--

Publish a Package

Publish a package of the MORE aggregator.

Method	POST http://more.locloud.eu:8080/MoRe_API/api/v1/packages/{packageId}/publish
---------------	--

Content Type	application/json
---------------------	------------------

Custom Headers	X-API-Key
-----------------------	-----------

Request	<code>{"schema": "EDM"}</code>
----------------	--------------------------------

Response	<code>{"msg": "Publish request received.", "packageId":1299, "schema": "EDM" }</code>
-----------------	---

Status	201 : CREATED 500 : INTERNAL_SERVER_ERROR
---------------	--

Reject a Package

Reject a package of the MORE aggregator.

Method	DELETE http://more.locloud.eu:8080/MoRe_API/api/v1/packages/{packageId}/reject
Content Type	application/json
Custom Headers	X-API-Key
Request	<code>{"message": "Reject Message"}</code>
Response	<code>{"msg": "Reject request received.", "packageId": 1299 }</code>
Status	201 : CREATED 500 : INTERNAL_SERVER_ERROR

Delete a Package

Delete a package from the MORE aggregator.

Method	POST http://more.locloud.eu:8080/MoRe_API/api/v1/packages/{packageId}/delete
Content Type	application/json
Custom Headers	X-API-Key
Request	
Response	<code>{"msg": "Delete request received.", "packageId": 1301 }</code>
Status	201 : CREATED 500 : INTERNAL_SERVER_ERROR

Withdraw a Package

Withdraw a package of the MORE aggregator.

Method	POST http://more.locloud.eu:8080/MoRe_API/api/v1/packages/{packageId}/withdraw
Content Type	application/json
Custom Headers	X-API-Key
Request	key
Response	<code>{"msg": "Withdraw request received.", "packageId": 1299 }</code>
Status	201 : CREATED 500 : INTERNAL_SERVER_ERROR

Get mappings

Get the mappings that correspond to a specific provider.

Method	GET http://more.locloud.eu:8080/MoRe_API/api/v1/packages/{packageId}/mappings
Content Type	application/json
Custom Headers	X-API-Key
Request	
Response	<code>[{"id": 5, "title": "OAI_DC to EDM"}]</code>
Status	200 : OK 500 : INTERNAL_SERVER_ERROR

Get rights

Get the rights appeared in all packages of each provider.

Method GET http://more.locloud.eu:8080/MoRe_API/api/v1/rights

Content Type application/json

Custom Headers X-API-Key

Request

Response

```
[
  {"id":1,"name":"The Public Domain Mark (PDM)"},
  {"id":2,"name":"Out of copyright - non commercial re-use (OOC-NC)"},
  {"id":3,"name":"The Creative Commons CC0 1.0 Universal Public Domain Dedication (CC0)"},
  {"id":4,"name":"Creative Commons - Attribution (BY)"},
  {"id":5,"name":"Creative Commons - Attribution, ShareAlike (BY-SA)"},
  {"id":6,"name":"Creative Commons - Attribution, No Derivatives (BY-ND)"},
  {"id":7,"name":"Creative Commons - Attribution, Non-Commercial (BY-NC)"},
  {"id":8,"name":"Creative Commons - Attribution, Non-Commercial, ShareAlike (BY-NC-SA)"},
  {"id":9,"name":"Creative Commons - Attribution, Non-Commercial, No Derivatives (BY-NC-ND)"},
  {"id":10,"name":"Free access - no re-use"},
  {"id":11,"name":"Paid access - no re-use"},
  {"id":12,"name":"Orphan work"},
]
```

Status 200 : OK
500 : INTERNAL_SERVER_ERROR

Get enrichment plans

Get the enrichment plans of the provider.

Method GET http://more.locloud.eu:8080/MoRe_API/api/v1/enrichmentPlans

Content Type application/json

Custom Headers X-API-Key

Request

Response

```
[
  {"id":1,"schema":"EDM", "title":"Standard EDM Enrichment Plan"}
]
```

Status 200 : OK
500 : INTERNAL_SERVER_ERROR

Get projects

Get the projects that a provider belongs to.

Method GET http://more.locloud.eu:8080/MoRe_API/api/v1/projects

Content Type application/json

Custom Headers X-API-Key

Request

Response

```
[
  {"acronym":"LoCloud", "projectId":3}
]
```

Status 200 : OK
500 : INTERNAL_SERVER_ERROR

Get schemas

Get the available schemas.

Method GET http://more.locloud.eu:8080/MoRe_API/api/v1/schemas

Content Type application/json

Custom Headers X-API-Key

Request

Response

```
[  
  {"schema": "CARARE", "schemaId": 1,}  
  {"schema": "CARARE20", "schemaId": 2,}  
  {"schema": "OAI_DC", "schemaId": 3,}  
  {"schema": "EDM", "schemaId": 4,}  
  {"schema": "eEDM", "schemaId": 5,}  
  {"schema": "ESE", "schemaId": 6,}  
  {"schema": "LIDO", "schemaId": 7,}  
]
```

Status 200 : OK
500 : INTERNAL_SERVER_ERROR

Annex II – Registry API

The first thing the user who wants to use the API must do, is to find his own API key from the Settings. This way he can access only his own records and manipulate them. He will need the key for the API calls.

Get Data Resources

Get all the Data Resources of the registry using some filters if it is needed.

Method	GET http://ariadne-registry.dcu.gr:8080/ariadneWeb/api/v1/dataResources									
Content Type	application/json									
Request	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Parameter</th> <th>Data Type</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>key</td> <td>String</td> <td>The API key of the user</td> </tr> <tr> <td>typeId</td> <td>Integer</td> <td>The type of the Data Resources (0:Collections 1:Datasets 2:Databases 3:GIS)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Parameter	Data Type	Description	key	String	The API key of the user	typeId	Integer	The type of the Data Resources (0:Collections 1:Datasets 2:Databases 3:GIS)
Parameter	Data Type	Description								
key	String	The API key of the user								
typeId	Integer	The type of the Data Resources (0:Collections 1:Datasets 2:Databases 3:GIS)								
Response	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Parameter</th> <th>Data Type</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>id</td> <td>Integer</td> <td>The id of each Data Resource</td> </tr> <tr> <td>name</td> <td>String</td> <td>The name of each Data Resource</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Parameter	Data Type	Description	id	Integer	The id of each Data Resource	name	String	The name of each Data Resource
Parameter	Data Type	Description								
id	Integer	The id of each Data Resource								
name	String	The name of each Data Resource								
Status	200 – SUCCESS 500 – INTERNAL_SERVER_ERROR									

Example

Request: {"key":"tUzQwU2T1RqBRuHC1ENJmtaopTMfWF6sHE7OrjRPzr98DiB","typeId":"1"}

Response: [{"id":20,"name":"CulturalItalia - Archaeology"}, {"id":33,"name":"Archaeological materials"}]

Get a Data Resource

Get all the properties of a specific Data Resource, given its id.

Method	GET http://ariadne-registry.dcu.gr:8080/ariadneWeb/api/v1/dataResources/{dataResourceId}												
Content type	application/json												
Request	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Parameter</th> <th>Data Type</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>key</td> <td>String</td> <td>The API key of the user</td> </tr> <tr> <td>id</td> <td>Integer</td> <td>The id of the specific Data Resource</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Parameter	Data Type	Description	key	String	The API key of the user	id	Integer	The id of the specific Data Resource			
Parameter	Data Type	Description											
key	String	The API key of the user											
id	Integer	The id of the specific Data Resource											
Response	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Parameter</th> <th>Data Type</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>id</td> <td>Integer</td> <td>The id of the specific Data Resource</td> </tr> <tr> <td>name</td> <td>String</td> <td>The name of the specific Data Resource</td> </tr> <tr> <td>properties</td> <td>List</td> <td>The list of the properties for the specific Data Resource</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Parameter	Data Type	Description	id	Integer	The id of the specific Data Resource	name	String	The name of the specific Data Resource	properties	List	The list of the properties for the specific Data Resource
Parameter	Data Type	Description											
id	Integer	The id of the specific Data Resource											
name	String	The name of the specific Data Resource											
properties	List	The list of the properties for the specific Data Resource											
Status	200 – SUCCESS 500 – INTERNAL_SERVER_ERROR												

Example

```

Request: {"key":"tUzQwU2P2T1RqBRHC1ENJmtaopTMfWF63sHE7OrjRPzr98DiBG"}
Response: {"id":41, "name":"dFMROe","properties":{"dct_issued":"1990s",
"dct:accessRights":"access only to 75565 records", ":scientificResponsible":"282",
"dcat:keyword":"Roman coins", "ARIADNEDistributionId":"44", "dct_identifier":"dat:41",
"dct:subject":"Roman coins", "dct:extent":"140000 records", "dct:audience":"researchers",
"ariadne_subject":"Artefacts", "dct_temporal":"116", "dct:creator":"281", "dct_language":"en",
"dct:description":"information on coins of the Preroman (Celtic) period and of Roman Imperial Times
found in Austria and in Romania", "dct:landingPage":"http://www.oeaw.ac.at/numismatik/
fmroe/content/suche.de.php", "dct_spatial":"108", ":dbms":"MySQL" }, "type":2}

```

Create a new Data Resource

Create a new Data Resource with all its properties. All mandatory elements must have a value for the successful creation.

Method	POST http://ariadne-registry.dcu.gr:8080/ariadneWeb/api/v1/dataResources															
Content Type	application/json															
Request	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Parameter</th> <th>Data Type</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>key</td> <td>String</td> <td>The API key of the user</td> </tr> <tr> <td>name</td> <td>String</td> <td>The name of the new Data Resource</td> </tr> <tr> <td>properties</td> <td>List</td> <td>The list of the properties for the new Data Resource</td> </tr> <tr> <td>type</td> <td>Integer</td> <td>The type of the Data Resource (0:Collections 1:Datasets 2:Databases 3:GIS)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Parameter	Data Type	Description	key	String	The API key of the user	name	String	The name of the new Data Resource	properties	List	The list of the properties for the new Data Resource	type	Integer	The type of the Data Resource (0:Collections 1:Datasets 2:Databases 3:GIS)
Parameter	Data Type	Description														
key	String	The API key of the user														
name	String	The name of the new Data Resource														
properties	List	The list of the properties for the new Data Resource														
type	Integer	The type of the Data Resource (0:Collections 1:Datasets 2:Databases 3:GIS)														

Response	Parameter	DataType	Description
	id	Integer	The id of the new Data Resource
	name	String	The name of the new Data Resource
	properties	List	The list of the properties for the new Data Resource
	type	Integer	The type of the Data Resource (0:Collections 1:Datasets 2:Databases 3:GIS)
Status	201 – SUCCESS 400 - BAD_REQUEST 500 – INTERNAL_SERVER_ERROR		

Example

```

Request: { "name": "API Example Database", "properties": { "ariadne_subject": "API Example Database",
  "dct_language": "en", "dbms": "MySQL" }, "type": 2 }
Response: { "id": 50820, "name": "API Example Database", "properties": { "dct_language": "en",
  "ariadne_subject": "API Example Database", "dbms": "MySQL" }, "type": 2 }

```

Get Distributions

Get all the Distributions of the registry.

Method	GET http://ariadne-registry.dcu.gr:8080/ariadneWeb/api/v1/distributions
Content Type	application/json

Request	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Parameter</th> <th>DataType</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>key</td> <td>String</td> <td>The API key of the user</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Parameter	DataType	Description	key	String	The API key of the user			
Parameter	DataType	Description								
key	String	The API key of the user								
Response	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Parameter</th> <th>DataType</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>id</td> <td>Integer</td> <td>The id of each Distribution</td> </tr> <tr> <td>name</td> <td>String</td> <td>The name of each Distribution</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Parameter	DataType	Description	id	Integer	The id of each Distribution	name	String	The name of each Distribution
Parameter	DataType	Description								
id	Integer	The id of each Distribution								
name	String	The name of each Distribution								
Status	<p>200 – SUCCESS</p> <p>500 – INTERNAL_SERVER_ERROR</p>									

Example

Request: {"key":"tUzQwU2P2T1RqBRHC1ENJmtaopTMfWF63sHE7OrjRPzr98DiBG"}

Response: [{"id":6,"name":"dati.culturaItalia"}, {"id":17,"name":"SITAR - Sistema Informativo Territoriale Archeologico di Roma"}]

Get a Distribution

Get all the the properties of a specific Distribution, given its id.

Method	GET http://ariadne-registry.dcu.gr:8080/ariadneWeb/api/v1/distributions/{distributionId}
Content Type	application/json

Request	Parameter	DataType	Description
	key	String	The API key of the user
	id	Integer	The id of the specific Distribution
Response	Parameter	DataType	Description
	id	Integer	The id of the specific Distribution
	name	String	The name of the specific Distribution
	properties	List	The list of the properties for the specific Distribution
Status	200 – SUCCESS		
	500 – INTERNAL_SERVER_ERROR		

Example

Request: {"key":"tUzQwU2P2T1RqBRHC1ENJmtaopTMfWF63sHE7OrjRPzr98DiBG"}

Response: { "id":45, "name":"DANS Web Portal", "properties":{ "dct_modified":"2014-01-01", "dcat:accessURL":"https://easy.dans.knaw.nl/", "dct_issued":"2014-01-01", "dct:description":"EASY online archiving system", } }

Create a new Distribution

Create a new Distribution with all its properties.

Method	POST http://ariadne-registry.dcu.gr:8080/ariadneWeb/api/v1/distributions
---------------	--

Content Type	application/json												
Request	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Parameter</th> <th>Data Type</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>key</td> <td>String</td> <td>The API key of the user</td> </tr> <tr> <td>name</td> <td>String</td> <td>The name of the new distribution</td> </tr> <tr> <td>properties</td> <td>List</td> <td>The list of the properties for the new distribution</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Parameter	Data Type	Description	key	String	The API key of the user	name	String	The name of the new distribution	properties	List	The list of the properties for the new distribution
Parameter	Data Type	Description											
key	String	The API key of the user											
name	String	The name of the new distribution											
properties	List	The list of the properties for the new distribution											
Response	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Parameter</th> <th>Data Type</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>id</td> <td>Integer</td> <td>The id of the new distribution</td> </tr> <tr> <td>name</td> <td>String</td> <td>The name of the new distribution</td> </tr> <tr> <td>properties</td> <td>List</td> <td>The list of the properties for the new distribution</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Parameter	Data Type	Description	id	Integer	The id of the new distribution	name	String	The name of the new distribution	properties	List	The list of the properties for the new distribution
Parameter	Data Type	Description											
id	Integer	The id of the new distribution											
name	String	The name of the new distribution											
properties	List	The list of the properties for the new distribution											
Status	201 – SUCCESS 400 - BAD_REQUEST 500 – INTERNAL_SERVER_ERROR												

Example

```

Request: {"key":"tUzQwU2P2T1RqBRHC1ENJmtaopTMfWF63sHE7OrjRPzr98DiBG", "name":"DANS
Web Portal", "properties":{"dct_modified":"2014-01-01",
"dcat:accessURL":"https://easy.dans.knaw.nl/", "dct_issued":"2014-01-01", "dct:description":"EASY
online archiving system", "dct:publisher":"5", "dct:licence":"8" } }
Response: { "id":45, "name":"DANS Web Portal", "properties":{"dct_modified":"2014-01-01",
"dcat:accessURL":"https://easy.dans.knaw.nl/", "dct_issued":"2014-01-01", "dct:description":"EASY
online archiving system", "dct:publisher":"5", "dct:licence":"8" } }

```

Get Data Formats

Get all the Data Formats of the registry.

Method	GET http://ariadne-registry.dcu.gr:8080/ariadneWeb/api/v1/dataFormats									
Content Type	application/json									
Request	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Parameter</th> <th>Data Type</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>key</td> <td>String</td> <td>The API key of the user</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Parameter	Data Type	Description	key	String	The API key of the user			
Parameter	Data Type	Description								
key	String	The API key of the user								
Response	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Parameter</th> <th>Data Type</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>id</td> <td>Integer</td> <td>The id of each Data Format</td> </tr> <tr> <td>name</td> <td>String</td> <td>The name of each Data Format</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Parameter	Data Type	Description	id	Integer	The id of each Data Format	name	String	The name of each Data Format
Parameter	Data Type	Description								
id	Integer	The id of each Data Format								
name	String	The name of each Data Format								
Status	200 – SUCCESS 500 – INTERNAL_SERVER_ERROR									

Example

Request: {"key":"tUzQwU2P2T1RqBRHC1ENJmtaopTMfWF63sHE7OrjRPzr98DiBG"}

Response: [{"id":149,"name":"aerial image"}, {"id":146,"name":" Information Source Data Format"}]

Get a Data Format

Get all the the properties of a specific Data Format, given its id.

Method	GET http://ariadne-registry.dcu.gr:8080/ariadneWeb/api/v1/dataFormats/{dataFormatId}												
Content Type	application/json												
Request	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Parameter</th> <th>DataType</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>key</td> <td>String</td> <td>The API key of the user</td> </tr> <tr> <td>id</td> <td>Integer</td> <td>The id of the specific Data Format</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Parameter	DataType	Description	key	String	The API key of the user	id	Integer	The id of the specific Data Format			
Parameter	DataType	Description											
key	String	The API key of the user											
id	Integer	The id of the specific Data Format											
Response	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Parameter</th> <th>DataType</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>id</td> <td>Integer</td> <td>The id of the specific Data Format</td> </tr> <tr> <td>name</td> <td>String</td> <td>The name of the specific Data Format</td> </tr> <tr> <td>properties</td> <td>List</td> <td>The list of the properties for the specific Data Format</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Parameter	DataType	Description	id	Integer	The id of the specific Data Format	name	String	The name of the specific Data Format	properties	List	The list of the properties for the specific Data Format
Parameter	DataType	Description											
id	Integer	The id of the specific Data Format											
name	String	The name of the specific Data Format											
properties	List	The list of the properties for the specific Data Format											
Status	200 – SUCCESS 500 – INTERNAL_SERVER_ERROR												

Example

Request: {"key":"tUzQwU2P2T1RqBRHC1ENJmtaopTMfWF63sHE7OrjRPzr98DiBG"}

Response: {"id":149, "name":"aerial image", "properties":{"dct:description":"JPG image", } }

Create a new Data Format

Create a new Data Format with all its properties.

Method	POST http://ariadne-registry.dcu.gr:8080/ariadneWeb/api/v1/dataFormats												
Content Type	application/json												
Request	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Parameter</th> <th>DataType</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>key</td> <td>String</td> <td>The API key of the user</td> </tr> <tr> <td>name</td> <td>String</td> <td>The name of the new data Format</td> </tr> <tr> <td>properties</td> <td>List</td> <td>The list of the properties for the new data Format</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Parameter	DataType	Description	key	String	The API key of the user	name	String	The name of the new data Format	properties	List	The list of the properties for the new data Format
Parameter	DataType	Description											
key	String	The API key of the user											
name	String	The name of the new data Format											
properties	List	The list of the properties for the new data Format											
Response	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Parameter</th> <th>DataType</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>id</td> <td>Integer</td> <td>The id of the new data Format</td> </tr> <tr> <td>name</td> <td>String</td> <td>The name of the new data Format</td> </tr> <tr> <td>properties</td> <td>List</td> <td>The list of the properties for the new data Format</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Parameter	DataType	Description	id	Integer	The id of the new data Format	name	String	The name of the new data Format	properties	List	The list of the properties for the new data Format
Parameter	DataType	Description											
id	Integer	The id of the new data Format											
name	String	The name of the new data Format											
properties	List	The list of the properties for the new data Format											
Status	201 – SUCCESS 400 - BAD_REQUEST 500 – INTERNAL_SERVER_ERROR												

Example

```

Request: {"key":"tUzQwU2P2T1RqBRHC1ENJmtaopTMfWF63sHE7OrjRPzr98DiBG", "name":"aerial
image", "properties":{"expressedIn":"xml", "dct:description":"JPG image", ":characterSet":"utf-8" }}
Response: { "id":149, "name":"aerial image", "properties":{"expressedIn":"xml",
"dct:description":"JPG image", ":characterSet":"utf-8" }}

```

Get foaf:Agents

Get all the foaf:Agent of the registry.

Method	GET http://ariadne-registry.dcu.gr:8080/ariadneWeb/api/v1/foafAgents									
Content Type	application/json									
Request	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Parameter</th> <th>Data Type</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>key</td> <td>String</td> <td>The API key of the user</td> </tr> <tr> <td>typeId</td> <td>Integer</td> <td>The type of the foaf:Agent (0:Agent 1:Organization)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Parameter	Data Type	Description	key	String	The API key of the user	typeId	Integer	The type of the foaf:Agent (0:Agent 1:Organization)
Parameter	Data Type	Description								
key	String	The API key of the user								
typeId	Integer	The type of the foaf:Agent (0:Agent 1:Organization)								
Response	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Parameter</th> <th>Data Type</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>id</td> <td>Integer</td> <td>The id of each foaf:Agent</td> </tr> <tr> <td>name</td> <td>String</td> <td>The name of each foaf:Agent</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Parameter	Data Type	Description	id	Integer	The id of each foaf:Agent	name	String	The name of each foaf:Agent
Parameter	Data Type	Description								
id	Integer	The id of each foaf:Agent								
name	String	The name of each foaf:Agent								
Status	200 – SUCCESS 500 – INTERNAL_SERVER_ERROR									

Example

Request: {"key":"tUzQwU2P2T1RqBRHC1ENJmtaopTMfWF63sHE7OrjRPzr98DiBG","typeId":"1"}
Response: [{"id":270,"name":"Emerenziana Usai"}, {"id":259,"name":"Mateja Belak"}]

Get a foaf:Agent

Get all the the properties of a specific Agent, given its id.

Method	GET http://ariadne-registry.dcu.gr:8080/ariadneWeb/api/v1/foafAgents/{foafAgentId}												
Content Type	application/json												
Request	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Parameter</th> <th>Data Type</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>key</td> <td>String</td> <td>The API key of the user</td> </tr> <tr> <td>id</td> <td>Integer</td> <td>The id of the specific foaf:Agent</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Parameter	Data Type	Description	key	String	The API key of the user	id	Integer	The id of the specific foaf:Agent			
Parameter	Data Type	Description											
key	String	The API key of the user											
id	Integer	The id of the specific foaf:Agent											
Response	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Parameter</th> <th>Data Type</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>id</td> <td>Integer</td> <td>The id of the specific foaf:Agent</td> </tr> <tr> <td>name</td> <td>String</td> <td>The name of the specific foaf:Agent</td> </tr> <tr> <td>properties</td> <td>List</td> <td>The list of the properties for the specific foaf:Agent</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Parameter	Data Type	Description	id	Integer	The id of the specific foaf:Agent	name	String	The name of the specific foaf:Agent	properties	List	The list of the properties for the specific foaf:Agent
Parameter	Data Type	Description											
id	Integer	The id of the specific foaf:Agent											
name	String	The name of the specific foaf:Agent											
properties	List	The list of the properties for the specific foaf:Agent											
Status	200 – SUCCESS 500 – INTERNAL_SERVER_ERROR												

Example

```

Request: {"key":"tUzQwU2P2T1RqBRHC1ENJmtaopTMfWF63sHE7OrjRPzr98DiBG"}
Response: { "id":110, "name":"Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS)", "properties":{"foaf_mbox":"info@dans.knaw.nl", }, "type":1 }

```

Create a new foaf:Agent

Create a new Agent with all its properties.

Method	POST http://ariadne-registry.dcu.gr:8080/ariadneWeb/api/v1/foafAgents															
Content Type	application/json															
Request	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Parameter</th> <th>Data Type</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>key</td> <td>String</td> <td>The API key of the user</td> </tr> <tr> <td>name</td> <td>String</td> <td>The name of the new foaf:Agent</td> </tr> <tr> <td>properties</td> <td>List</td> <td>The list of the properties for the new foaf:Agent</td> </tr> <tr> <td>type</td> <td>Integer</td> <td>The type of the foaf:Agent (0:Agent 1:Organization)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Parameter	Data Type	Description	key	String	The API key of the user	name	String	The name of the new foaf:Agent	properties	List	The list of the properties for the new foaf:Agent	type	Integer	The type of the foaf:Agent (0:Agent 1:Organization)
Parameter	Data Type	Description														
key	String	The API key of the user														
name	String	The name of the new foaf:Agent														
properties	List	The list of the properties for the new foaf:Agent														
type	Integer	The type of the foaf:Agent (0:Agent 1:Organization)														
Response	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Parameter</th> <th>Data Type</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>id</td> <td>Integer</td> <td>The id of the new foaf:Agent</td> </tr> <tr> <td>name</td> <td>String</td> <td>The name of the new foaf:Agent</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Parameter	Data Type	Description	id	Integer	The id of the new foaf:Agent	name	String	The name of the new foaf:Agent						
Parameter	Data Type	Description														
id	Integer	The id of the new foaf:Agent														
name	String	The name of the new foaf:Agent														

	<p>properties List The list of the properties for the new foaf:Agent</p> <p>type Integer The type of the foaf:Agents (0:Agent 1:Organization)</p>
Status	<p>201 – SUCCESS</p> <p>400 - BAD_REQUEST</p> <p>500 – INTERNAL_SERVER_ERROR</p>

Example

```

Request: {"key":"tUzQwU2P2T1RqBRHC1ENJmtaopTMfWF63sHE7OrjRPzr98DiBG", "name":"Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS)", "properties":{"foaf_mbox":"info@dans.knaw.nl", "foaf:phone":"888999214", "foaf:homepage":"www.example.com", "foaf:skypeID":"dans" }, "type":1 }
Response: { "id":110, "name":"Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS)", "properties":{"foaf_mbox":"info@dans.knaw.nl", "foaf:phone":"888999214", "foaf:homepage":"www.example.com", "foaf:skypeID":"dans" }, "type":1 }
    
```

Annex III –Thesauri Available through MORE

This table presents some (of the most relevant) thesauri that MORE is able to access through the TemaTres API. These thesauri are accessible to the end user through the subject collections enrichment micro-services.

Author	Name	Subject	Language
University of California, Santa Barbara	Alexandria Digital Library Feature Type Thesaurus	Science & Technology: places, geographica	English
Royal Commission on the Ancient and Historical Monuments of Scotland (RCAHMS)	Archeological Objects Thesaurus Scotland	Objects made by human activity	English
English Heritage	Archeological Sciences Thesaurus	Techniques, recovery methods and materials associated with archaeological sciences	English
English Heritage	Building Materials Thesaurus	Main constructional material types (eg. the walls) for indexing of monuments	English
English Heritage	Components Thesaurus	Terminology covering divisions and structural elements of a building or monument	English
American Folklore Society	Ethnographic Thesaurus	Social sciences: ethnographic, folklore, united states, etnomusicology	English
English Heritage	Event Type Thesaurus	Terminology used for recording archaeological and architectural investigative, data collection exercises; from intrusive interventions to non damaging surveys	English

Author	Name	Subject	Language
English Heritage	Evidence Thesaurus	Terminology covering the existing physical remains of a monument, or the means by which a monument has been identified where no physical remains exist	English
English Heritage	FISH Archeological Objects Thesaurus	Recording of archaeological objects in Britain and Ireland covering all historical periods	English
GEMET Thesaurus	General Multilingual Environmental Thesaurus GEMET	environment, policies	Dutch, English, French, German, Italian, Portuguese, Spanish
Federation Internationale des Archives du Film (FIAF)	General Subject headings for Film Archives	Arts & Humanities: films, films archives, cinema	English
The Discovery Programme	Irish Monuments	Irish monuments	English
The Discovery Programme	Irish Periods	Irish periods	English
Royal Commission on the Ancient and Historical Monuments of Scotland (RCAHMS)	Maritime Craft Thesaurus Scotland	Types of craft that survive as wrecks, or are documented as losses, in Scottish maritime waters	English
English Heritage	Maritime Craft Type Thesaurus	Craft types which survive as wrecks in English Heritage's maritime record	English
English Heritage and Royal Commission on the Historical Monuments of England	MDA Archaeological Objects Thesaurus	Social sciences: archaeological objects; museums; vocabulary	English

Author	Name	Subject	Language
Royal Commission on the Ancient and Historical Monuments of Wales (RCAHMW)	Monument Thesaurus Wales	Classification of monument types in Wales by function	English
Royal Commission on the Ancient and Historical Monuments of Scotland (RCAHMS)	Monument Type Thesaurus	Monument types relating to the archaeological and built heritage of Scotland	English, Scottish Gaelic for some terms
English Heritage	Period Thesaurus	English Heritage Periods List	English
Royal Commission on the Ancient and Historical Monuments of Wales (RCAHMW)	Period Thesaurus Wales	A list of periods for use in Wales	English
Bibliographic Standards Committee of the Rare Books and Manuscripts Section (ACRL/ALA)	Relator Terms for Use in Rare Book and Special Collections Cataloguing	Arts & Humanities: Rare Book; Special Collection	English
Universidad de León	Tesauro de Ciencias de la Documentación	Social sciences: library sciences, information sciences, documentation, librarianship	Spanish
Library of Congress. Prints and Photographs Division	Thesaurus for Graphic Materials 1: Subject Terms	Arts & Humanities: graphic materials, subject terms	English
Library of Congress. Prints and Photographs Division	Thesaurus for Graphic Materials 2: Genre and Physical Characteristic Terms	Arts & Humanities: graphic materials	English
Ministero per i Beni e le Attività Culturali	Thesaurus PICO 4.1	Arts & Humanities: italian culture, heritage	English, Italian

Author	Name	Subject	Language
UKAT	UK Archival Thesaurus (UKAT)	General reference: archives, ukat, united kingdom	English
UNESCO	UNESCO thesaurus	General reference: education, culture, social and human sciences, information and communication, politics, law, economic science	English, French, Spanish